

Understanding the determinants of Restaurant Switching intentions: The Utilization of Push-Pull-Mooring framework

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Abstract:

This study empirically investigates the applicability of the push-pull-mooring (PPM) framework on restaurant switching intentions. The employed framework is the theoretical extension of the current PPM Model, which is uncommon in the literature. The antecedents of this research are push variables (satiation with food, satiation with service, satiation with atmosphere); pull (post dining regret, alternative attractiveness); the moderating variables are mooring (self-control, place attachment, OSL). The study uses Chinese restaurants market, which is highly competitive and diverse in terms product offerings and quality customer services in complex environment. The study employed variance based Structural Equation modeling with Partial Least Square estimators. The results show that push, pull and mooring variables have positive significant impact on restaurant switching intentions. It is also evident with statistical analysis that pull factors more favorably contributed as compared to push factors. The findings also reflect that mooring variable significantly moderates between push factors and restaurant switching intentions and pull factors and restaurant switching intentions. The findings are robust to the policy implications.

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1. Introduction

There is an extensive growth in the restaurant industry all over the world. In the USA, roughly eight million restaurant franchises exist, which have differently sized outlets for example smaller, medium and larger and according to National Restaurant Association (NRA) sales has hit \$825 billion in 2018. These restaurants include multinational chains running thousands of outlets across the world (Line, 2018). The restaurant industry has developed extensively in China as well and the trend among people to go restaurants in China has increased over the past years. For example, In 2016, 3.5 trillion yuan (\$507 billion) was spent dining out in China (Huang, 2017). The forecasted food service value of China by 2022 is around 820 billion USD out of which the estimated sales value of only full-service restaurants in China is nearly 610 billion US dollars (Textor, 2020). With the increase in number of restaurants, individuals have more than one option for selecting a restaurant. Individuals tend to select what they perceive as a best option, however if the service encounter was not satisfactory at a particular restaurant or the same purchases was made frequently customers might go for other options available (Kwon & Jain, 2009).

The previous studies on switching behavior following PPM Model has focused more on, survey of consumers' assessment of product or service as push factors (e.g. low quality, dissatisfaction, low commitment, and low trust) (Bansal et al., 2005; Lehto, Park, & Gordon, 2015; Hou, Chern, Chen, & Chen, 2011; H. H. Chang, Wang, & Li, 2017), alternative attractiveness (I. Chang, Liu, & Chen, 2014; Chang et al., 2017) as pull factors, and as mooring variable switching cost is often used (Xu, Yang, & Cheng, 2014). More specifically this research focus on that restaurant switching intentions are engendered by the push factors such as satiation (satiation with food, satiation with service, and satiation with atmosphere), pull factors such as post purchase regret and alternative attractiveness, and also the mooring factors such as place attachment, self-control, and OSL. The research empirically explores the applicability of, push-pull-mooring (PPM) model to restaurant switching. Thus, it contributes in a variety of ways to the literature of service marketing, consumer behavior and consumer psychology. First, the PPM framework is designed as a unifying paradigm for understanding the switching behaviors of consumers in the restaurant. The marketing literature currently lacks a comprehensive restaurant switching model. Cronin et al., (2000) debated that composite frameworks of consumers' decision - making in service environments are essential to avoid the likelihood of strategy development which either overemphasize or understate the importance of certain factors. This problem is answered by the PPM model and offers theoretical rationale for including certain predictor variables. Second, the study explores how the PPM framework and relevant literature can also be used to propose new restaurant switching determinants beyond satisfaction (i.e. satiation, place attachment, self-control and post dining regret) and to grasp other factors of switching restaurants.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Push-Pull-Mooring Theory: The push-pull variable of the PPM migration framework has quite a long history, going back to the 19th century. Ravenstein (1885) proposed the "Laws of Migration," to the Royal Statistical Society in 1885 and formed the groundwork for the push-pull paradigm (Bansal et al., 2005). And according to push-pull paradigm, there are variables at the origins that motivate (push) the person to leave and forces at the destination that draw (pull) the person to enter (Lewis, 1982). Traditionally, these study focused only on real migrants, those who have migrated, not someone who has opted not to migrate. Researchers

therefore centered their attention on finding only the negative factors at the origin (i.e. the push variables) and the positive factors at the destination (hence the pull variables).

According to its conceptualization, the migrants' decision are based on an assessment of the pushing and pull considerations; moreover, this assessment is carried out within the framework of the person's own social and personal context. Migration choices may be influenced by factors such as personal attachments, personal distress or migration costs. Jackson (1986) altered Lee's (1966) findings of "intervening obstacles" as he claimed that migration frameworks should contain "intervening variables," not barriers, because these factors either promote or impede migration. Similarly, the principle of moorings was introduced by Longino (1992), which Moon (1995) later included in the push-pull paradigm of migration. Moorings refers to existence of cultural and geographical aspects that act to promote or impede migration decisions. Thus, moorings extend the concept of intervention variables; they include all the personal, cultural and social variables which influence the decision to choose whether or not move. Migration study indicates that immigration choices are made on interpretations of macro-level push and pull parameters, but that micro-level parameters, like personal and social factors, also play a significant role. In order to predict migration, it is therefore important to analyze migrants' perceptions of variables at source that might act to drive them away (push variables), perceptions of variables at destination that might act to attract migrants to them (pull variables) and perceptions of individual variables that act either to encourage or hinder migration decisions (mooring variables) (Bansal et al., 2005).

2.2 Restaurant Switching Intentions: A restaurant is a place where a service employee serves ready food and drink and customers pay for that food and service. Consequently, consumers demand a certain level of quality and normally judge quality and the dining experience in general based on a variety of attributes. Generally, restaurant features are allied with services, food and environments (Ha & Jang, 2013a). Restaurant marketing research regards these as the basic elements influencing consumer loyalty and post-consumption behaviors (Ha & Jang, 2012). Previous studies have emphasized the importance and effects on potential behavior of food quality, such as taste, portion, menu and healthy options. (Clark & Wood, 1999; Jang et al., 2013; Line et al., 2016; Park & Jang, 2014b; Ryu et al. 2012; Sulek & Hensley, 2004). Clark & Wood (1999) in a restaurant option, indicated that food quality is the main factor. Further, Line (2018) and Sulek & Hensley (2004) found that food quality is important for customer satisfaction and future behavioral intentions. Service quality is also a key factor in quality management that affects customer satisfaction and value (Chen & Peng, 2018; Ha & Jang, 2013b; Line et al., 2016; V. A. Zeithaml, Berry, & Parasuraman, 1996). These studies emphasized the significance of service quality in shaping consumer behaviors in consumption situations. Improvements in service quality develop the repatronage intentions of customers and decrease unfavorable behaviors, such as complaining or spreading negative word-of-mouth. The physical environment has also been considered a perilous factor that positively affects the perception of customers of their dining experiences (Ha & Jang, 2013b; Park & Jang, 2014b; Ryu et al., 2010; Ryu & Jang, 2008).

Restaurants can generally be categorized into three categories: fast food restaurants, casual dining restaurants and fine dining restaurants. A fast-food restaurant stresses fast service and relatively low food prices and consumers expect to consume food from disposable containers directly (Ha & Jang, 2013a). These characteristics of fast food restaurants emphasize comfort and quality, which are the most important features of the fast food market (Line, 2018). In a comfortable environment where table service is offered, a casual dining restaurant serves moderately-priced food. In other words, casual restaurants are a cheaper version of fine

dining restaurants and are mostly used as a venue to celebrate an event (Park & Jang, 2014b). Casual dining restaurants therefore aim to attract customers by offering high quality food and facilities at an affordable cost, while maintaining a friendly environment so that family and friends can share a meal.

Fine dining restaurants provide full-service restaurants with dedicated meal courses, a well-trained staff offering high-quality service and a luxurious environment. While most fast food restaurants and casual dining restaurants have well-known brands that account for the restaurant industry's wide market share, most fine-dining restaurants are owned by individual operators, and their market share is still relatively small. Fine dining restaurants, however, are seen as a vital segment of the restaurant industry because trends in food and service and dining traditions usually originate from fine dining restaurants (Almohaimmed, 2021). If the service providers are well aware of the reasons behind customer service switching decisions, they will devise better strategies to discourage consumer switching and recover those that have already switched to alternatives. In addition, less consumer switching would lead to more profitability, as a result of the notion that customer retention costs a business less than attracting a new one (V. Zeithaml, 2000). Previous hospitality researchers paid more attention to perceived quality, satisfaction, switching costs and service failures and, in particular, to the first two. Scholars and practitioners have both assumed that satisfaction leads to loyalty, and have therefore emphasized the study of customer satisfaction levels and their impact (García & Rafael, 2019). The need to look for other factors to understand switching behavior has been acknowledged without sacrificing the undoubted effect of satisfaction and perceived quality on the decision to change service provider. (Liao et al., 2017; Sánchez García & Curras-Perez, 2019). In reality, not all customers who want to change providers are dissatisfied as this shift is attributable to other reasons, such as satiation, in some cases (with food, service quality and atmosphere), personality traits (self-control, OSL), place attachment, presence of attractive alternative or post purchase regret (Sánchez García & Curras-Perez, 2019; Yan et al., 2019; Bora et al., 2018; Line, 2018).

2.2.1 Push factors and restaurant switching intentions: The word "satiation" refers to reduction in overall pleasure upon prolonged exposure of similar stimulus (Coombs & Avrunin, 1977; Oliver, 1993; Line et al., 2016; Yan et al., 2019). In other terms, satiation could be described as an association between positive and negative effects (Berlyne, 1970) and individuals will gradually become fulfilled if they are consistently introduced to the similar stimuli. In the restaurant sector, customers are repeatedly exposed to similar styles of cuisine as well as the same franchise (or chain) restaurants. In other terms, after eating at the same restaurant, restaurant customers can frequently experience satisfaction since they do not provide much to know about the particular restaurant and their average utility is reduced (Ha & Jang, 2012). Satisfaction, as noted above, is already mentioned amongst the most key determinants in decreasing consumer switching intentions. However, available research in consumer research indicates that the delighted consumers can also exhibit elevated levels of switching behavior (Redden & Galak, 2012; Ha & Jang, 2013b; Park & Jang, 2014b; Sánchez García & Curras-Perez, 2019).

H1: *Higher the satiation with food, satiation with service and satiation with atmosphere, higher the likelihood consumers will intend to switch restaurants.*

2.2.2 Pull factors and restaurant switching intentions: Regret is referred as an arousal of a negative feeling after a buyer's choice which he/she wishes not have been made at all (Tsiros & Mittal, 2000). Regret is linked with the post buying stage and might be experienced with

any kind of buying decision (García & Rafael, 2019). In the sense of restaurant switching activities, this means that if customers regret their choice of restaurant as they feel that some other dining experience in another substitute restaurant could have been nicer, they might end up moving to some other venue even if they are satisfied (Tsiros & Mittal, 2000). Indeed, Zeelenberg & Pieters, (2004) received support for the argument of the direct impact of post-purchase regret (in our context, post dining regret) on consumer switching intention. Alternative attractiveness is described as buyers perception of the consumer on availability of other need satisfying alternatives in the market (García & Rafael, 2019). If the benefits of an alternative are perceived higher than the attained one, consumers will possibly move to the alternative (Chuah, Marimuthu, Kandampully, & Bilgihan, 2017). Briefly, the extent of quality information of alternatives weaken consumer relationship with existing supplier and encourages to switch (Anton, Camarero, & Carrero, 2007). Dissatisfied consumers may choose to stay with the same service seller if they believes that there are not much alternative available in the marketplace (Anderson & Narus, 1990). On the contrary, consumers despite being satisfied can choose from other alternatives if they perceive them better during future purchase situations (Park & Jang, 2014b).

H2: *Higher the post purchase regret, and alternative attractiveness of other restaurants, higher the possibility that consumers will intend to switch restaurants.*

2.2.3 Mooring factors and restaurant switching intentions: Self-control is an individual's capacity to change/control its own responses and states (Baumeister, 2002). Self-control is a well-established personality trait factor, able to elaborate significant differences in individuals' behavior. People with higher self-control are better in controlling their behavior, than of people, with low self-control. People with personality trait as low self-control losses control of their loyal behavior directed towards a brand, place or store and are more likely to switch even if they intend to remain loyal. On the contrary people with high self-control reliable for their consistent behavior and likely not to get de-tracked by the various sales offers (Sevilla, Lu, & Kahn, 2019). Customers with higher self-control, would be experiencing less levels of satiation with repeated experience than, customers with less self-control. This will eventually result in lower level of restaurant switching intention. In accordance with OSLT, repeated consumption of restaurant is likely to decrease the novelty and complexity of service choices (Raju, 1980). Compared with low-OSL individuals, high-OSL individuals are more prone to seek activities that are novel and different. To maintain the preferred level of stimulation, high-OSL individuals are more apt to try new consumption experience. Consequently, high-OSL individuals may be found to exhibit more variety-seeking behaviors than low-OSL individuals.

Place attachment is described as "the bonding between a person and a place" (Rosenbaum, Ward, Walker, & Ostrom, 2007). Individuals with strong attachments drives positive emotional effects, such as emotional constancy, feeling secure, and comfort (Hummon, 1992). In consumer context, a customer when attached to a place, feels "at home" and carries feelings of belonging and comfort (Rosenbaum & Montoya, 2007; Yuksel, Yuksel, & Bilim, 2010). Also, place attachment may enhance the overall benefits a consumer receives by positive interaction with others at the place (Line, 2018). Therefore, if managers wants consumers to continuously patronize their visits to the restaurants their focus must be on fulfilling consumers' needs, give them positive experience through quality services, and their visit must be joyful.

H3: The likelihood that consumers will intend to switch restaurants is lower when individual's self-control, place attachment is higher and optimal stimulation level is lower.

H4: Mooring factors moderates the association between push factors and consumer's restaurant switching intentions. Precisely, stronger the mooring factors, the weaker is the association between push variables and restaurant switching intention.

H5: Mooring factors moderates the association between pull factors and consumer's restaurant switching intentions. Precisely, stronger the mooring factors, the weaker is the association between pull variables and restaurant switching intention.

Figure 1: Proposed conceptual framework

2.3 Research Methodology

This research study is explanatory in nature, as the variables of the study are not used in this context before. The design of current study is the cross-sectional as data is collected from sample only once. All the Chinese consumers of full service restaurants, having several dining experiences, are considered as sampling unit of current study. Chinese restaurant consumers are selected as research setting due to several reasons. The ever-increasing urbanization and increase of China's middle-class population is fueling the rise in sales of the food service industry. The restaurant industry has developed extensively in China and the trend among people to go restaurants has increased over the past years. The HRI sector is also highly competitive in China's Tier 1 cities (i.e. Shanghai, Beijing, Shenzhen, Guangzhou) and is growing fast in Tier 2 and Tier 3 cities (Bean, Meador, Xinping, & Han, 2018). As China is highly competitive in terms of restaurant industry, therefore, restaurant consumers are more

responsive to switching calls. Also, it is evident that restaurant managers will be facing more customer switching challenges in Tier 1 than any other region.

2.4 Instruments and measures

To measure our constructs, we adapt established scales from existing literature. All constructs are grounded using a scale of strongly disagree (= 1) to strongly agree (= 5) on a five point Likert-scale format. To measure satiation (satiation with food, satiation with service, and satiation with atmosphere), we adapt 10 items scale from Line et al., (2016). Satiation of food is operationalized as how much the dinner is bored with the taste, menus, and presentation of food. Satiation with service is operationalized as, how much the dinner is bored with service procedures, style and relationship with servers. Whereas, satiation with atmosphere is operationalized as the dinners boredom with interior design, decoration, table layout and table settings. Post dining regret scale consists of four-item and is adapted from Patterson & Smith, (2003). It is operationalized as how much dinner feels sorry, regretted, harmed, and disappointed at choosing the restaurant. The alternative attractiveness is measured by four-item scale adapted from (Han et al., 2011). It is operationalized as the availability, choice, certainness, confidence of dinners of alternative restaurants.

The scale of self-control is also adapted from Park & Jang, (2014a) and the scale consists of four-item. Self-control is operationalized as consumers' ability to resist, refuse, and control the change calls and remain firm in current actions. Furthermore, we measure "OSL" with four-item scale each adapted from Park & Jang, (2014a). OSL is operationalized as consumers' willingness to try, experience, like and prefer new food items. The six-item scale on place attachment is adopted from Line, (2018). Place attachment is operationalized as how much the restaurant consumer enjoy, praise, think, attached and patronized with the restaurant. Dinners switching intentions is the measured by six-item scale adapted from Line, (2018). We operationalize it as dinners' choice of other familiar, known and tried restaurant or unfamiliar, new and different restaurant.

2.5 Statistical Approach

PLS-SEM uses power analysis to validate the statistical power of the model and determine the statistical adequacy of sample size. Hence, we conducted a post hoc power analysis test using the G*Power 3.1 version to assess whether the sample size of 197 is adequate to validate the strength of the research. The significance level (α), sample size (N) and Effect Size (ES) of the population are required to test the power of the model. Cohen et al. [197] quantified effect size using the formula, $ES = R^2 / 1 - R^2$. Hence, using G* power with 8 constructs, 5% level of significance and effect size of 0.3 (medium), the 98% power is achieved. Fig (2), it is evident that the sample size of 197 is enough to achieve adequate power for statistical analysis.

Figure 2 Statistical power analysis for sample

3. Results and Discussions

Table 1 Demographic of subjects

Demographic information	Frequency	%
Gender		
Male	204	52.9
Female	181	47.1
Marital status		
Single	131	34.1
Married	254	65.9
Age (years)		
18-25	106	27.5
26-30	129	33.5
31-40	86	22.3
41-50	46	12.0
Above 50	18	4.7
Education		
High School	23	6.0
Senior High School	60	15.6
Bachelor's Degree	161	41.8
Master's Degree	119	30.9
Doctorate	22	5.7
Income (RMB per month)		
Under 3000	14	3.6
3000-4999	41	10.7
5000-9999	135	35.1
10,000-15000	109	28.3
Over 15000	86	22.3
Restaurant Category		
Casual	85	22.1
Fast Casual	69	17.9
Fine Dining	187	48.6
Upscale	44	11.4
Frequency of Visit (In previous month)		
Once	73	19.0
Twice	128	33.2
03 Times	113	29.4
More than 03 times	71	18.4

Source : Authors

Table 1 is about the analytical (demographic plus socio-economic variables) variables, and show their frequency and percentage. The analytical variables are Gender, Marital Status, Age, Income, Education, Restaurant Category and Frequency of Visit. The gender is categorized as the male and female. Marital status is categorized as single and married. Age is categorized as 18-25 years, 26-30 years, 31-40 years, 41-50 years and above 50 years. Income (in RMB) is categorized as under 3000, 3000 to 4999, 5000 to 9999, 10,000 to 15000 and Over 15000. Education is categorized in different levels of education such as; High School, Senior High School, Bachelor's degree, Master's degree and Doctorate. Restaurant category takes into account four different categories of restaurants; Casual, Fast Casual, Fine Dining and Upscale. Whereas, frequency of visit (in previous month) is divided into four categories; Once, Twice, Three (03) times and more than three (03) times.

Table 2 Correlational matrix and VIF

Constructs	VIF	AA	OSL	PA	PDR	SATA	SATF	SATS	SLF	SWI
AA	2.79	1								
OSL	1.04	0.385	1							
PA	1.33	0.043	0.222	1						
PDR	2.53	0.502	0.245	0.015	1					
SATA	2.97	0.058	0.127	0.507	-0.074	1				
SATF	1.99	0.016	0.218	0.563	-0.13	0.533	1			
SATS	1.60	-0.048	0.143	0.513	-0.081	0.505	0.48	1		
SLF	2.32	0.229	0.37	0.182	0.272	0.139	0.192	0.11	1	
SWI	1.18	0.304	0.214	0.213	0.151	0.195	0.152	0.24	0.122	1

Note: AA= Alternative Attractiveness; OSL=Optimal Stimulation Level; PA=Place Attachment; PDR=Post Dining Regret; SATA=Satiation with Atmosphere; SATF=Satiation with Food; SATS=Satiation with Service; SWI=Switching Intention

We used cross-sectional data with single source of data collection. Because the single source of data collection, we will use Harman's single-factor test of Podsakoff et al. (2003) to examine for common method variance (CMV) among data. We applied Harman's single-factor test to assess for spurious covariance among constructs due to a common method of data collection. An explanatory factor analysis will have performed for all items of constructs and results of first three factors cumulative variance should be greater than 50%. The study also used Kock (2015) and (Bagozzi et al. (1991) approach to robust the presence and detection of CMV. Kock (2015) criteria dictate inner values of all constructs below 3.0. Moreover, (Bagozzi et al. (1991) approach uses correctional matrix of constructs and asked for absence of CMV if the correlation between and pair of constructs is below 0.90. As evident from the Table 2, VIF values of all constructs ranges 1.08-2.97 well within threshold recommended by Kock (2015). Similarly, the correction between constructs reveal no relationships of concern as the maximum correlation is 0.563, and this fulfills criteria of the study.

Table 3 Results of direct paths

Hypotheses	Paths	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics	Bias-corrected confidence interval (95%)	Decision
Hypothesis: H1	PUSH --> SWI	0.220**	0.219	0.056	3.932	[0.117:0.372]	Supported
Hypothesis: H2	PULL --> SWI	0.266***	0.216	0.057	4.7	[0.147:0.373]	Supported
Hypothesis: H3	MOORING --> SWI	0.174*	0.278	0.06	2.651	[0.122: 0.276]	Supported

Note: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$

For assessing the direct path of the hypotheses, the current study used 5000 bootstrap confidence interval (95%) biased corrected using structural equation modelling (SEM) in smartPLS 3.0. First, the results of hypotheses in respect of antecedents' effects on switching intentions were assessed. The results showed significant effects of push factors on switch intentions (PUSH --> SWI: $b = 0.220$, $t = 3.93$). This supported our hypothesis H1. In sequence, related to the effect of PULL factors on switching intentions demonstrated significant positive influence (PULL --> SWI: $b = 0.266$, $t = 4.70$). The result supported our hypothesis H2. Similarly, the result of Mooring on switching intentions showed significant positive effects (MOORING --> SWI: $b = 0.174$, $t = 2.650$), thus supported our hypothesis H3. Overall, the results related to our first set of hypotheses related to antecedents (i.e., PUSH, PULL, and MOORING factors) were supported. The direct paths are summarized in Table 3.

Table 4: Results of the moderating effect

Hypotheses	Paths	Effect size (b)	Boot SE	Bias-corrected CI. 95%	Decision
Hypothesis: H6	PUSH*MOORING -->SWI	0.126*	0.320	[0.017, 0.268]	Supported
Hypothesis: H7	PULL*MOORING --> SWI	0.153**	3.157	[0.098, 0.392]	Supported

Note: ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$

Moderating effects of Mooring: We assessed that mooring factors have significant direct effects on consumers' switching intentions (i.e., H3). For checking the moderating influence of mooring factors, we adopted the product indicator approach in smartPLS 3.0 and made interaction effects for both our moderation effects (i.e., PULL and PUSH interaction with MOORING). The first set of interaction effects (PUSH*MOORING) on consumers' switching intentions showed significant effects (PUSH*MOORING -->SWI: $b = 0.126$, $t = 0.326$). This supported our hypothesis H4. The second set of interaction effects (PULL*MOORING) showed that mooring significantly decreases switching intentions (PULL*MOORING --> SWI: $b = 0.153$, $t = 3.157$). Therefore, it supported the hypothesis H5.

4. Conclusions and Implications

This research gives a variety of theoretical contributions. First, this research is the first one to follow the migration theory PPM model in order to explain consumer behavior in the food

service industry. Second, focusing on the common ground between the first-order dimensions affecting the consumer's switching behavior, this research describes the push, pull and mooring variables and checked the utility of the second-order structure model to more concisely conceptualize the concepts. Thirdly, in the previous literature, the pull factor was mostly described by the attractiveness of the alternatives, (Bansal et al., 2005; Hsieh, Hsieh, Chiu, & Feng, 2012; Zhang, Zhao, Cheung, & Lee, 2014). However, this research extends the pull attributes by identifying more specific pull dimensions (i.e., post dining regret) derived from the concept of post purchase regret used in literature (García & Rafael, 2019; Liao et al., 2017; Sánchez-García & Currás-Pérez, 2011; Zeelenberg & Pieters, 2004). Finally, the research study showed that among the three drivers of restaurant switching intention, mooring factors are the weakest. In other words, diners move to other restaurants because they're either bored or feel regretted by their prior dining experiences or because they are satiated (i.e with food, service and atmosphere). The place attachment and the personal characteristics of diners plays a minor role in the function of diner switching.

The dominant variables in past switching behavioral research have been latent variables including service quality, price, satisfaction, and trust. Conversely, this study discovered that push factors such as satiation with food, satiation with service, and atmospheric satiation, and also pull factors such as post-dinning regret and alternative attractiveness, plays more important role especially in the context of restaurant switching. Variables like i.e., service quality, customer satisfaction, switching cost, customer trust, and service price are predominated in prior service switching behavior studies. Our results indicate that more consideration should be given to variables which have been overlooked in previous switching behavior research. (i.e., satiation, post dining regret, place attachment and self-control).

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